

Delamination, Durability and Damage Tolerance of Laminated Composite Materials

T. Kevin O'Brien
U.S. Army Aerostructures Directorate
NASA Langley Research Center
Hampton, VA

ABSTRACT

Research exploring the role of delamination on the durability and damage tolerance of advanced composite materials is reviewed. Recent studies on the characterization of composite delamination are summarized. Recent analytical solutions for interlaminar stresses and strain energy release rates associated with common sources of delamination are also reviewed. The role of delamination in low velocity impact, residual compression strength, and in fatigue is highlighted. Delamination is shown to be the common damage mode observed in all of these problems. A Damage Threshold/Fail-safety concept for addressing composite damage tolerance is discussed.

1. INTRODUCTION

As high strength, low density fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites are considered for highly strained primary aircraft structures, increased attention is being devoted to the understanding and characterization of composite delamination. Delamination may result from low velocity impact, from eccentricities in structural load paths that induce out-of-plane- loads, or from discontinuities in the structure that create local interlaminar stress singularities. The purpose of this review paper is to highlight some recent research studies on composite delamination. Work by the author and others at NASA Langley are highlighted along with some significant results in the literature.

2. DELAMINATION CHARACTERIZATION

2.1 Monotonic loading Composite delamination is most commonly characterized using fracture mechanics test methods. Critical values of strain energy release rate are measured to quantify the interlaminar fracture toughness. Because composite delamination may arise as a result of a combination of interlaminar normal tensile stresses and interlaminar shear stresses, the delamination may be a mixture of the three classical fracture modes. These include an opening mode I, a sliding shear mode II, and a scissoring shear mode III.

The mode I interlaminar fracture toughness is typically measured using the Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) test [1]. In the DCB test, delaminations start at the insert and grow in a stable manner along the beam. However, because the beams are unidirectional, the fiber nesting that is typically present results in fiber bridging across the delamination plane, between the two beams, as the delamination grows [2,3]. This fiber bridging causes the apparent toughness to increase with delamination length (fig.1) [4]. However, because fiber bridging is not present initially, the onset value of G_{Ic} measured from the insert may still be representative of natural delamination, assuming the insert is sufficiently thin (fig.2) [4].

The mode II interlaminar fracture toughness is usually measured using the End Notched Flexure (ENF) test. The ENF test involves loading a unidirectional beam, with a thin insert at the midplane, in three point bending. Delaminations start at the insert and grow in an unstable manner along the beam [5]. Therefore, only the onset of mode II delamination is measured. Recently, a stabilized version was proposed whereby the test is controlled to a constant shear displacement at the delamination front [6]. However, any value measured after the onset will have shear damage at the delamination front that may influence G_{IIc} measurements [7,8].

Presently, there are no commonly accepted test methods for measuring mode III scissoring delamination. A Split Cantilever Beam (SCB) was proposed for this purpose [9]. However, this test was demonstrated to contain a significant mode II contribution [10]. Many delaminations that occur naturally are mixed-mode, resulting from the presence of both interlaminar tension and shear stresses. To date, all the mixed-mode tests that have been prescribed are combinations of mode I and mode II [11-14]. Recently, a Mixed-Mode Bending (MMB) test was developed that utilizes the same unidirectional beam tested in the DCB and ENF tests [13,14]. The MMB test provides toughness measurements over a wide ratio of mode I and mode II that may be used with the DCB and ENF measurements to develop mixed mode delamination failure criteria.

2.2 Cyclic Loading The same tests that are commonly used to measure interlaminar fracture toughness have been used to characterize delamination in fatigue. Early work attempted to simulate crack growth laws for metals by correlating the rate of delamination growth with cycles, da/dN , with the maximum cyclic strain energy release rate, G_{max} , or the cyclic range of G [15,16]. However, retardation occurs in the DCB test due to the fiber bridging that develops once the delamination forms [17]. Figure 3 shows da/dN data generated on unidirectional DCB AS4/PEEK specimens. As the delamination grows, $G_{I_{max}}$ decreases and fiber bridging develops. Hence, the generic value of the slope of the log-log plot, and the apparent threshold values, is questionable. Furthermore, even with fiber bridging present, these power law curves are much steeper, i.e., they have much larger slopes on a log-log plot of da/dN versus G , than similar curves for most metals. Hence, a very small error in estimated load, and hence G , will result in a large error in delamination growth rate. Therefore, the classical damage tolerance approach of tracking crack growth may not be practical for composite delamination.

An alternate approach that characterizes delamination onset under cyclic loads by plotting the maximum cyclic G as a function of cycles to delamination onset has been proposed. This characterization was generated using the DCB and ENF tests [17]. Figure 4 shows a plot of $G_{I_{max}}$ as a function of the number of cycles to delamination onset. The curve fit to the data appears to reach an asymptote, or threshold G value, near 10^6 cycles.

3. DELAMINATION ANALYSIS

Many solutions have been generated for the strain energy release rate, G , associated with delamination growth. Typically, these G solutions are generated using a finite element analysis and the virtual crack closure technique (VCCT) [18]. This technique yields mode I, mode II, and mode III strain energy release rate components. The total G is obtained by summing these three modal components, and may be verified using a global energy balance analysis.

3.1 Edge Delamination Early solutions in the literature showed that the strain energy release rate for edge delamination was independent of delamination size and varied with the ply thickness and the square of the applied strain [19]. Finite element analyses using the VCCT technique showed that the independent modes were also independent of delamination length [20]. These edge delamination solutions have been extended to the case of a laminate with an open hole, subjected to remote tension or compression loading, using the rotated straight edge technique [21]. A higher order plate theory (HPT) technique for calculating the various modal components was later developed and tested by comparing to finite element (FEM) analyses of the numerous edge delamination cases that result from the rotated straight edge analogy for the open hole [22]. Figure 5 shows the variation in G_I and

G_{III} with angular position around the hole for a delamination in a particular interface. Similar plots may be generated for each unique interface in the laminate. These G calculations may be used to identify the most likely location for delamination to appear around the hole boundary.

3.2 Delaminations from Matrix Ply Cracks Early studies contrasted the difference in edge delaminations with the more localized delaminations that form at the intersection of the matrix crack and the stress free edge [23]. This localized delamination commonly occurs in fatigue, and is the primary reason that fatigue failures occur in tension [24]. Recent 3D finite element models of delaminations emanating at the intersection of matrix cracks with free edges have demonstrated that very large tensile interlaminar normal stresses may develop at these locations [25,26]. Also, as shown in fig.6, G components have the greatest magnitude near the intersection of the matrix crack and the free edge.

3.3 Ply Drops in Tapered Laminates In many structural applications, composite laminates are tapered to reduce thickness. This tapering is typically achieved by dropping internal plies. These terminated plies create discontinuities that result in local stress singularities. Several investigators have studied the interlaminar stresses that develop in tapered laminates [27,28]. Recently, a study was completed where the strain energy release rate associated with delamination growth from a discontinuity in a tapered laminate was developed [29]. As shown in fig.7, strain energy release rate solutions were generated for delaminations growing from the juncture between the thin and tapered regions. The analysis was performed using the virtual crack closure technique (VCCT) as well as an energy balance technique that yielded similar results.

3.4 Delamination from buckled sublaminates One source of composite delamination growth is the local instability that arises from the buckling of a delaminated region under compression loading. The most commonly analyzed problem consists of a laminate with a through width delamination near one surface. Both the load at which the sublaminates will buckle and the strain energy release rate for further delamination growth have been calculated [30]. Several authors have extended this analysis to an embedded circular or elliptical delamination [31,32]. Strain energy release rate solutions have been generated and used with G_{Ic} values to predict delamination growth. Figure 8 shows that the predicted strain for the onset of sublaminates buckling varies with the depth of the initial delamination [31].

4. DELAMINATION IN LOW VELOCITY IMPACT

Composite laminates subjected to low velocity impacts often experience extreme damage that may not be visible on the impacted surface. This damage may lead to significant reductions in the ability of the laminate to carry the desired compression load.

4.1 Impact Damage Several studies have been conducted to characterize the nature of impact damage in composite laminates [33-34]. Typically, the high transverse shear stresses induced during the impact create a conical pattern of matrix cracks in each layer that initiate local delaminations between the layers. Recently, several researchers have developed a rationale called the "K" rule for anticipating the damage pattern based on the laminate layup and stacking sequence [35-36]. This rule allows the analyst to anticipate the kind of "spiral staircase" pattern of interconnecting matrix cracks and delaminations that develop during a low velocity impact on a laminate with arbitrary layup. Figure 9 shows the pattern that develops through the thickness of a quasi-isotropic laminate [36].

4.2 Compression After Impact Recently, a model for predicting the residual compression strength for quasi-isotropic laminates having impact damage simulated by the "K" rule has been developed [37,38]. Impact damage was simulated by a spiral array of transverse cracks and delaminations forming 4-ply thick circular sublaminates. The analysis steps to predict the effects of this damage included a model of sublaminates stability, an equivalent reduced stiffness calculation for the buckled damage zone, and a finite element analysis of stress redistribution that accurately modeled finite width effects. The sublaminates properties affecting damage tolerance were found to be the reduced bending stiffness, sublaminates thickness, and diameter. The critical material properties affecting damage tolerance included moduli and the undamaged compression strength.

5. DELAMINATION IN FATIGUE

Delamination is commonly observed in fatigue. Composite laminates and structural configurations that do not delaminate before final failure under monotonic loads will often exhibit stable delamination formation and growth in fatigue.

5.1 Unnotched Laminates Delaminations typically form at straight edges in unnotched laminates due to the Poisson mismatch created by the particular layup or stacking sequence [19,20]. Furthermore, delaminations also form at the straight edge as a result of matrix cracking [23,26]. Recently, a tension fatigue life prediction methodology was proposed based on predicting the accumulation of delaminations through the laminate thickness [24]. Unnotched laminates subjected to compression fatigue also fail as a result of the accumulation of delamination through the laminate thickness [39]. For stitched laminates, the stitching causes earlier onset of delamination, but the rate of delamination growth appears to be retarded [40]. However, just as was observed for unstitched laminates, the ultimate compression failure results from an accumulation of delaminations through the laminate thickness.

5.2 Tapered Laminates Finite element models of delamination in tapered laminates showed that the initial delamination growing from the juncture between the thin and tapered region consisted primarily of an opening (mode I) component [29]. Calculated G values have been compared to cyclic DCB data to predict the cycles to delamination onset in unidirectional and multi-ply tapered laminates [41,42].

5.3 Notched Laminates Open hole fatigue data is often used to compare one damage tolerance concept to another. For example, figure 10a shows the open hole compression (OHC) fatigue S-N data for a stitched AS4/3501-6 laminate and an unstitched IM7/8551-7 tape laminate, both containing a 1/4 inch diameter hole [43]. Both materials exhibit similar fatigue behavior, with the degradation in compression strength with cycles resulting from the formation, growth, and accumulation through the thickness of delaminations that begin either at the straight edge, or at the hole boundary.

Figure 10b shows fatigue results for the same two types of laminates that were first subjected to low velocity impacts. Although the compression failure strain after impact (CAI) is 0.6%, or greater, for the toughened matrix and stitched composites, their fatigue strength continuously decreases, just as was observed for the open hole laminate. However, brittle matrix composites, like the unstitched AS4/3501-6 laminates, tend to have relatively flat S-N curves following low velocity impacts [44]. The difference in the shape of the S-N curves following low velocity impact may be attributed to the type and severity of loading that is required to create the same accumulation of delaminations through the laminate thickness. For the brittle matrix composite, delaminations form in nearly every interface during the impact. Hence further cyclic loading creates very little new damage, i.e., few new delaminated interfaces are formed through the laminate thickness. However, in the toughened matrix and stitched composites, only a few interfaces are delaminated during the impact. However, subsequent cyclic loading will cause delaminations to form at the matrix cracks created by the impact, at the intersection of angle plies and free edges, or at the stitches, until nearly all the interfaces are delaminated. When the damage becomes extensive through the thickness, after 10^6 cycles or greater, the compression strengths become similar to those measured for the brittle matrix composites that were subjected to low velocity impact only (fig.10b).

6. DAMAGE THRESHOLD/ FAIL-SAFETY CONCEPT

Recently, a Damage Threshold/Fail Safety philosophy was proposed for ensuring that composite structures are both sufficiently durable for economy of operation, and adequately damage tolerant for safety of operation [45]. In this approach, matrix cracks are assumed to exist throughout the off-axis plies. Delamination onset is predicted using a strain energy release rate characterization. Delamination growth is accounted for in one of three ways: either analytically, using delamination growth laws in conjunction with strain energy

release rate analyses; experimentally, using measured stiffness loss; or conservatively, assuming delamination onset corresponds to catastrophic growth. Fail safety is assessed by accounting for the accumulation of delaminations through the thickness. This concept was demonstrated for predicting tension fatigue life. Furthermore, techniques for applying this concept were also outlined for compression fatigue, tension/compression fatigue, and compression strength following low velocity impact.

7. SUMMARY

Research exploring the role of delamination on the durability and damage tolerance of advanced composite materials was reviewed. Recent studies on the characterization of composite delamination were summarized. Recent analytical solutions for interlaminar stresses and strain energy release rates associated with common sources of delamination were also reviewed. The role of delamination in low velocity impact, residual compression strength, and in fatigue were highlighted. Delamination was shown to be the common damage mode observed in all of these problems. A Damage Threshold/Fail-safety concept for addressing composite damage tolerance was summarized.

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1. Increase in G_{Ic} with delamination length due to fiber bridging in a DCB test [4].

2. Effect of insert thickness on G_{Ic} [4].

3. Mode I fatigue delamination growth rates [17].

4. $G_{I\max}$ as a function of cycles to delamination onset [17]

5. Comparison of finite element (FEM) and Higher-order Plate Theory (HPT) analyses of G components for delamination at an open hole boundary [22].

6. Variation of normalized G and G components along a uniform delamination front originating at a 90 degree matrix ply crack ($h =$ ply thickness) [26].

7. Normalized strain energy release rate for delamination originating in a tapered laminate ($h =$ ply thickness) [29].

8. Predicted delamination onset strains as a function of initial delamination area for different delaminations (indicated by ply number from the top surface) in a compression loaded laminate [31].

9. Schematic of impact damage accumulation through the thickness of a $(-45/0/45/90)_{3s}$ laminate [36].

10. Open hole compression and compression after impact as a function of fatigue cycles to failure in stitched and unstitched graphite epoxy coupons [43].

